

The Impact of Government Expenditure and Investment on Poverty in Gorontalo Province

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Abstract:- The results of this study indicate that there are variables in this study that influence poverty in Gorontalo Province, namely the labor absorption variable. Meanwhile, the variables of regional government expenditure in the fields of capital expenditure and personnel expenditure and economic growth have no effect on the poverty variable in Gorontalo Province in 2007-2022. This is due to the start of the development of industrial centers in Gorontalo Province which will ultimately have an impact on the absorption of the workforce in Gorontalo Province.

The results of this study indicate that there is one variable that has an indirect effect on poverty in Gorontalo Province, that variable is personnel spending through economic growth on poverty in Gorontalo Province. Meanwhile, the variables of regional government spending in capital expenditure and investment and economic growth do not have an indirect effect on poverty in Gorontalo Province through economic growth and employment. This is because the portion of the regular budget for personnel spending is experiencing a positive trend or tends to increase and through a budget policy that focuses on personnel spending to continue to employ auxiliary (honorary) workers in government agencies it is considered to be on target in reducing poverty.

Keywords:- Government Expenditure; Investment; Poverty.

I. INTRODUCTION

Poverty is still a serious problem in Indonesia that is difficult to solve, because the dimensions of poverty have widened into other aspects. From a problem that was initially unidimensional, it has now developed into a multidimensional problem. In simple terms, poverty itself can be interpreted as a situation where a person is unable to meet basic needs such as food, clothing, shelter, and cannot access education and health (BPS 2022).

According to Todaro and Smith (2015), poverty that occurs in developing countries results from the interaction between the following 6 characteristics: (1) The level of national income of developing countries is relatively low, and the rate of economic growth is relatively slow; (2) Per capita income is still low and growth is very slow; (3) The distribution of income is very unequal or very unequal; (4) The majority of the population in Third World countries must live under the pressure of absolute poverty; (5) Poor and very limited health facilities and services, malnutrition and many disease outbreaks; (6) Educational facilities in most developing countries as well as curriculum content are still relatively irrelevant or inadequate, because they do not have assets as a source of income as well as because the socio-economic structure does not provide opportunities for the poor to get out of the endless cycle of poverty.

Poverty in Gorontalo Province is still a very serious problem, the poverty rate for Gorontalo Province is still above the national level and is in 5th position with the highest poverty rate for all provinces in Indonesia (BPS 2022). However, poverty in Gorontalo, in terms of percentage and number of poor people over the last 5 years has experienced a downward trend. The percentage of poor people in Gorontalo Province in September 2018 managed to fall to 15.31 percent, or decreased 0.21 percent compared to March 2019, and decreased 0.52 percent compared to the same period in 2018. The number of poor people in September 2019 was 184,710 thousand people, decreased by 1.32 thousand people compared to the position in March 2019, and decreased by 3.59 thousand people compared to September 2018 of 188.30 thousand people. The number of poor people in March 2022 was 185.44 thousand people, an increase of 0.84 thousand people in September 2021 and a decrease of 0.85 thousand people in March 2021.

The percentage of poor people in urban areas in March 2022 was recorded at 3.97 percent, a decrease of 0.09 percentage point from the condition in September 2021 which was recorded at 4.06 percent.

Fig 1 Economic Growth and Poverty Percentage in Gorontalo Province, 2010-2022.

Source: Central Statistics Agency of Gorontalo Province

Poverty alleviation efforts have also been carried out at the district and city levels in Gorontalo Province as evidenced by regional development activities. This development aims to create ongoing economic growth and experience a change in circulation for the better and in the end will be able to increase regional income, thereby creating employment opportunities and improving people's welfare, as well as overcoming the problem of poverty in Gorontalo. All of this is contained in the 2017-2022 Gorontalo Province Regional Medium-Term Development Plan (RPJMD) document regarding the main focus of the poverty alleviation program through 14 priority programs launched by the Gorontalo Provincial government.

The problem of poverty is not limited to looking at the number and percentage of the population. Other dimensions must also be considered, such as the depth of poverty (poverty gap index-p1) and poverty severity (poverty security index-p1). Policies carried out by the government in addition to reducing the number of poor people must also address the level of depth and severity of poverty. In 2016 the poverty depth index increased by 4.12 percent from 3.97 percent in the previous year. This increase was also followed by the high poverty severity index for Gorontalo Province in the same year of 1.47 percent from 1.24 percent in the previous year. In 2022 the poverty depth index is 3.04 percent, an increase of 0.18 percent from the previous year 2021 which amounted to 2.86 percent while for the poverty severity index in 2022 0.85 percent, this figure has increased 0.13 percent from the conditions in the previous year 2021 which amounted to 0.72 percent. This indicates that the spending gap among the poor fluctuates.

II. METHODS

The research approach uses a quantitative approach which is carried out in the form of Two Stage Least Square (2SLS) analysis with time series data in an annual period, namely from 2007 to 2022.

The location of this research was conducted in Gorontalo Province. The research took the form of collecting secondary data from the websites of the Investment Coordinating Board, Gorontalo Central Bureau of Statistics, Gorontalo Representative Office of Bank Indonesia, Gorontalo Provincial Finance Agency, Gorontalo Province Investment, ESDM and Transmigration Office (DPMESDMTRANS), etc. The time of this research was conducted in November 2022.

The data used in this research is secondary data, namely Gorontalo Province Capital Expenditure Data for 2007-2022. Government Expenditure in Personnel Expenditures in 2007-2022. Investment (PMA and PMDN) 2007-2022. Absorption of Labor in Gorontalo Province in 2007-2022, Economic Growth in Gorontalo Province in 2007-2022, and Poverty Percentage (PO) of Gorontalo Province in 2007-2022.

The data used in this study were obtained from various sources such as the Indonesian Central Bureau of Statistics, the Central Bureau of Statistics for Gorontalo Province (www.bps.go.id), Bank Indonesia Gorontalo Representative Office, the ministry of finance (statistik.kemenkeu.go.id), the Investment Coordination, Gorontalo Provincial Finance Agency, and Gorontalo Provincial Investment, ESDM and Transmigration Office (DPMESDMTRANS). Documentation of data relating to the object under study and using other literature that is in accordance with this research.

The data collection technique used was library research where library research is a research method to obtain information from literature related to this research, such as research journals, theses, dissertations and other published books related to this research. The data collection technique used is direct recording in the form of time series data for the period (2007-2022).

The data analysis technique used for this research model is 2SLS (Two Stage Least Square) using STATA software. To assess the relationship between variables that have been previously determined based on the theory. First, the data is processed to be presented as a description and general description for research and simultaneous equation regression analysis. Second, simultaneous equation regression analysis which will be estimated according to the Reduced Form coefficients. Third, the results of the reduced form coefficient estimation of the simultaneous equation will be analyzed both in the form of a direct and indirect relationship with (significant level $\alpha=0.05$) a number of implications and recommendations as a result of the findings of this study.

III. RESULT

The direct effect of capital expenditure (X1) on economic growth (Y1) in 2007-2022 is shown by a coefficient value of $-.0013$ with a significance of $0.000 < 0.05$ and is stated to have an effect in a negative direction. The direct effect of capital expenditure (X1) on employment (Y2) in 2007-2022 is shown by a coefficient value of $.3313$ with a significance of $0.001 < 0.05$ and is stated to have a positive effect. The direct effect of capital expenditure in Gorontalo Province in 2007-2022 (X1) on poverty (Y3) is indicated by a coefficient value of 0.147 with a significance of $0.140 > 0.05$ and is stated to have no effect on a positive directional relationship.

The direct effect of personnel expenditure (X2) on economic growth (Y1) in Gorontalo Province in 2007-2022 is shown by a coefficient value of $-.0010$ with a significance of $0.625 > 0.05$ and is stated to have no effect with a negative direction relationship. The direct effect of personnel spending (X2) on employment (Y2) in Gorontalo Province in 2007-2022 is shown by a coefficient value of $.1837$ with a significance of $0.000 < 0.05$ and is stated to have a positive effect.

The direct effect of investment (X3) on economic growth (Y1) in Gorontalo Province in 2007-2022 is indicated by a coefficient value of $.0002$ with a significance of $0.419 > 0.05$ and is stated to have no effect on the direction of a positive relationship. The direct effect of investment in Gorontalo Province in 2007-2022 (X3) on employment (Y2) is shown by a coefficient value of $.0125$ with a significance of $0.100 > 0.05$ and is stated to have no effect on the direction of a positive relationship.

The direct effect of economic growth (Y1) on employment (Y2) in Gorontalo Province in 2007-2022 is shown by a coefficient value of $10,601$ with a significance of $0.039 < 0.05$ and is stated to have a positive effect. The effect of Gorontalo Province's economic growth (Y1) on poverty (Y3) in 2007-2022 is shown by a coefficient value of $.3058$

with a significance of $0.480 > 0.05$ and is stated to have no effect on the direction of a positive relationship. The effect of Gorontalo province's employment absorption (Y2) on poverty (Y3) in 2007-2022 is shown by a coefficient value of $.0487$ with a significance of $0.000 < 0.05$ and is stated to have a positive effect.

A detailed explanation of the form and magnitude of the direct effect, indirect effect and total effect of capital expenditures, personnel expenditures and investment on poverty through economic growth and employment in table 5.2 – table 5.4. The analysis was carried out in accordance with the order of the hypotheses that had been stated previously.

The indirect effect of capital expenditure (X1) on poverty (Y3) through economic growth (Y1) in Gorontalo Province in 2007-2022 with a p-value of $0.086 > 0.05$, which means it has no effect. The indirect effect of capital expenditure (X1) on poverty (Y3) through employment (Y2) in 2007-2022 with a p-value of $0.062 > 0.05$, which means it has no effect.

The indirect effect of personnel spending (X2) on poverty (Y3) is through economic growth (Y1) with a p-value of $0.005 < 0.05$ which means it has an effect. The effect of personnel spending (X2) on poverty (Y3) through employment (Y2) in 2007-2022 (Y1) p-value of $0.634 > 0.05$, which means it has no effect.

The indirect effect of investment (X3) on poverty (Y3) is through economic growth (Y1) with a p-value of $0.108 > 0.05$ which means it has no effect. The effect of investment (X3) on poverty (Y3) through employment (Y2) in 2007-2022 p-value of $0.452 > 0.05$, which means it has no effect. The effect of economic growth (Y1) on poverty (Y3) through employment (Y2) with a p-value of $0.065 > 0.05$, which means it has no effect.

IV. DISCUSSION

The direct effect of capital expenditure (X1) on economic growth (Y1) in 2007-2022 is shown by a coefficient value of $-.0013$ with a significance of $0.000 < 0.05$. This means that regional government spending in the field of capital expenditure has a negative relationship to economic growth in Gorontalo Province in the 2007-2022 research period.

The direct effect of capital expenditure (X1) on employment (Y2) in 2007-2022 is shown by a coefficient value of $.3313$ with a significance of $0.001 < 0.05$ and is stated to have a positive effect. This shows that capital expenditure has a positive effect on employment.

This finding is in line with the results of research conducted by Rika Aria Dwi (2015). The results of his research show that capital expenditure has a positive effect of 0.000333 and is significant.

The direct effect of capital expenditure in Gorontalo Province in 2007-2022 (X1) on poverty (Y3) is indicated by a coefficient value of 0.147 with a significance of $0.140 > 0.05$ and is stated to have no effect on a positive directional

relationship. This shows that capital expenditure has not been able to reduce the percentage of poverty.

In the 2016-2018 period, the amount of capital expenditure has decreased for the purchase of productive assets of the Gorontalo Provincial government. In 2015 the capital expenditure allocation was 344 billion rupiah, in the following year 2016 the expenditure allocation was 297 billion rupiah and in 2018 there was a decrease to 255 billion rupiah.

This finding contradicts the results of previous research conducted by Akhmad (2015). The results of his research show that capital expenditure has a negative effect on the poverty level variable.

The effect of local government spending on capital expenditure (X2) on economic growth (Y1) in 2007-2022 is shown by a coefficient value of -0.0070 with a significance of $0.002 < 0.05$. This shows that local government spending in the field of personnel expenditure has a negative relationship to economic growth in Gorontalo Province in the 2007-2022 research period.

Government spending that is used to finance all matters related to ongoing government activities will later encourage consumption levels and can then drive other sectors. Which in turn can have a positive impact on economic growth in the area. Availability of budget allocations to keep budgeting honorary workers able to absorb jobs.

The direct effect of personnel expenditure (X2) on economic growth (Y1) in Gorontalo Province in 2007-2022 is shown by a coefficient value of -0.0010 with a significance of $0.625 > 0.05$ and is stated to have no effect with a negative direction relationship. This shows that personnel spending has not been able to influence employment in Gorontalo Province.

The direct effect of investment (X3) on economic growth (Y1) in Gorontalo Province in 2007-2022 is indicated by a coefficient value of $.0002$ with a significance of $0.419 > 0.05$ and is stated to have no effect on the direction of a positive relationship. This indicates that the amount of investment in Gorontalo Province has not been able to affect economic growth in Gorontalo Province

As a relatively new area, Gorontalo Province still needs a lot of incoming funds. Both from foreign investment and domestic investment. This is to support increased development in the region. Gorontalo Province is carrying out development in various sectors, both physical and non-physical. Community service is also a top priority in development. This province has just been formed and has investment potential in the agriculture, fisheries, mining and industrial sectors. For this reason, the government is also trying to open new areas by inviting investors to come and invest in Gorontalo Province. However, there are several obstacles that are still a common concern, namely, the availability of adequate infrastructure to carry out or increase export and import capacity.

The direct effect of investment in Gorontalo Province in 2007-2022 (X3) on employment (Y2) is shown by a coefficient value of $.0125$ with a significance of $0.100 > 0.05$ and is stated to have no effect on the direction of a positive relationship. This shows that the amount of investment in Gorontalo Province has not been able to affect the level of employment in Gorontalo Province.

The trend of investment in Gorontalo province is highly volatile and tends to be towards the use of technology rather than the use of direct labour. So that it has not been able to have an effect/contribution to employment, or in other words the ability of the Gorontalo Province workforce has not met the standards of companies or institutions.

The direct effect of economic growth (Y1) on employment (Y2) in Gorontalo Province in 2007-2022 is shown by a coefficient value of $10,601$ with a significance of $0.039 < 0.05$ and is stated to have a positive effect.

In carrying out the development program of the Gorontalo Provincial government, there are several groupings of fields or sectors, which include several sectors including agriculture, mining, industry, electricity, building, trade, transportation, finance and services where the above sectors absorb a lot of labor.

The results of this study contradict the research conducted by Muhammad Sokian et al. The results of his research show that economic growth has no significant effect on the dependent variable of labor. Any increase or decrease in economic growth does not affect the increase or decrease in the number of workers in Sarolangun Regency. Economic growth has a negative direction and has a significant impact on poverty rates, poverty depth, and poverty severity levels through the workforce in Sarolangun District.

V. CONCLUSION

Based on the data processed and analyzed, it can be concluded:

- The results of this study indicate that there are variables in this study that affect poverty in Gorontalo Province, namely the labor absorption variable. Meanwhile, the variables of regional government expenditure in the fields of capital expenditure and personnel expenditure and economic growth have no effect on the poverty variable in Gorontalo Province in 2007-2022. This is due to the development of industrial centers in Gorontalo Province which will ultimately have an impact on the absorption of the workforce in Gorontalo Province.
- The results of this study indicate that there is one variable that has an indirect effect on poverty in Gorontalo Province, that variable is personnel spending through economic growth on poverty in Gorontalo Province. Meanwhile, the variables of regional government spending in the fields of capital expenditure and investment and economic growth do not have an indirect effect on poverty in Gorontalo Province through economic growth and employment. This is because the portion of the regular budget for personnel

spending is experiencing a positive trend or tends to increase and through a budget policy that focuses on personnel spending to continue to employ auxiliary (honorary) staff in government agencies it is considered to be on target in reducing poverty.

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